

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING AN ARTISTIC TEXT AND METHODS OF TRANSLATION

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Annotation: This article will focus on the problems in the translation of artistic prose and will reveal some appropriate solutions, and will also reflect the views of scientists about the main methods of translation used in translation.

Keywords: translation, artistic text, translation methods, equivalent translation, culture-specific words, grammatical differences.

Translating artistic texts, that is, Novels, Stories, short stories, requires special attention. It is a type of literary creativity in which the written work of one language is recreated in another. However, the source language, and the languages being translated belong to different cultural groups, the first problem facing the translator is to find terms in their language that best match the meaning of specific words. Many consider the translation of literary works as one of the most complex forms of translation, since it should convey more content, culture, worldview, the main idea than the translation of the text.

The literary translator must also be qualified to translate emotions, cultural nuances, humor and other subtle elements of the work. In fact, translators should reflect in translation not sentences, meaning. Therefore, the text should be considered as a whole. In contrast, Peter Newmark (1988) interprets the translation as "showing the meaning of a text in a different language in the way the author intended the text". The source text contains examples of "edges" promoted in a dignified way by Lawrence Venuti (1995): "discursive differences, archaism, slang, literary identities and convention".

Each text is unique, and at the same time the text turned into another language is a separate work. No text is completely original, because the language itself in its essence is, firstly, a non-verbal state, and secondly, because each character and each phrase is a translation of another character. However, an artistic text can be turned around without losing any authenticity: all texts are original, since each translation is unique. Each translation, up to a certain point, is invented, and therefore it constitutes a unique text. Walter Benjamin (1996) states that the translation does not show the original text, with no connection to the dialogue.

Translation Theorists view dynamic equivalence as translation code; it is according to this code that the translator seeks to show the meaning of the original in such a way that translation readers will surely enjoy the text that is usually performed by those who read the source text. The Shape of the original text is changed frequently; but if the change follows the rules of the back-shift in the source language, contextual consistency in transmission, and transformation in the language of receptors, the message is preserved and the translation is reliable. They argue that the dynamic equivalence in translation is more than the correct conveyance of information. In other words, we translate texts, sentences, etc., and this process helps us to communicate with other people with different cultural roots. "The translation mark often tells of the different times and gaps between cultural authority and its performance practices".

The most characteristic problems faced by translators are: unreadable text, missing links, several constructions of grammar, dialect terms and neologisms, irrational ambiguous terminology, incomprehensible abbreviations, untranslatable words, deliberate misnomer, separate cultural references, etc. Nevertheless, there are some theorists who believe that "literal translation" is impossible here. They show three main reasons that support their positions:

1. Because a certain word in one language often indicates meanings that include several words in another language;

2. Since grammatical concepts (verb tenses, singular / dual / plural markers, etc;

3. Because idioms belonging to one language and culture can absolutely surprise speakers from another language and culture.

In addition, prose translators can combine some of the following methods to effectively solve translation problems. Back translation: "comparing back translation with the original text is sometimes used to verify the accuracy of the original translation..."(Crystal, 2004: 3). This is one of the most familiar practices used to search for equivalents: translating elements from the source language into the target language and free translation of the artistic text into the source language.

Conclusion. Translation is a complex activity, and several difficulties arise in the translation process, since each language describes the world in a different way and has its own grammatical structure, rules of grammar and syntactic discrepancy. For example, in Greek there are separate words for "light blue" and "dark blue", while in other languages such as Welsh and Japanese there are only words that mean "blue" or "green" or something in between. The difficulty in translation is that both the content and the style are already present in the original and without the result you will have to do your best to repeat them as they are in a completely different language

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